

**Response to the US National Institutes of Health (NIH)
Request for Information (RFI)
*Promoting Equity in Global Health Research***

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Background (e.g., academic institutions, extramural, intramural researchers, private sector, and the public): Ambassador for Ethics and Science, European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Future & Research Data Alliance (RDA); Executive Director, Good Clinical Practice Alliance - Europe (GCPA) & Strategic Initiative for Developing Capacity in Ethical Review (SIDCER)

RFI Request (20 May to 1 August 2022 for Responses)

Issued by

Fogarty International Center ([FIC](#))

National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute ([NHLBI](#))

National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Diseases ([NIAID](#))

Eunice Kennedy Shriver National Institute of Child Health and Human Development ([NICHD](#))

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Purpose

This Notice is a Request for Information (RFI) on approaches NIH can take to promote greater equity in global health research, particularly research that engages scientists in low and middle-income countries (LMICs) ([REF](#)).

Background

As a global leader in biomedical and behavioral research, NIH is committed to supporting collaborative international research that harnesses the rich diversity of the biomedical workforce to advance timely solutions to global health challenges. Therefore, NIH has a responsibility to identify and address, to the extent possible given its mission, the challenges and barriers to equitable research, which for the purposes of this RFI is defined as research collaboration that is inclusive, elevates underrepresented voices and groups, and demonstrates fairness of opportunity and fair process ([REF](#)). This interest builds on NIH's long-standing practice of funding highly meritorious research throughout the world, both through direct awards to non-U.S. institutions and indirectly through awards to U.S. institutions that then use those awards to support collaborating foreign institutions. NIH has long encouraged international research collaborations and is interested in exploring opportunities to further encourage and facilitate research that is conducted equitably, in true partnership with collaborators and for the benefit of all participants.

In practice, equity in global research may be achieved through collaborations based on true partnership, shared leadership, joint applications and publications, and the inclusion of previously disadvantaged individuals as research partners. Through this RFI, NIH seeks ideas and specific actions that NIH may consider to encourage the expansion and quality of such global research collaborations, particularly with scientists and institutions in LMICs.

NIH welcomes the global dialogue around increased equity in global health research and seeks to respond with insights and ideas generated through this RFI. In addition to promoting an ever more collaborative research environment, NIH recognizes that equitable research processes, strengthened scientific and research administrative capacity, the inclusion and sustaining of local talent and expertise, and a focus on local health priorities will advance scientific discovery and the development of more effective, appropriate, and sustainable health interventions. This RFI is intended to improve NIH's understanding of potential research funding, priority setting, and administrative practices and strategies that could encourage or facilitate equitable global health research.

Information Requested

Respondents to this RFI are invited to provide input regarding current NIH practices that might be revised or new practices that could be implemented to enhance collaborative international research equity and the generation of mutual benefits and shared leadership; and to propose practical ideas that could help NIH enhance these practices. NIH acknowledges that thought leaders in this regard are widely distributed throughout the U.S. and the international scientific, academic, and public health communities. NIH looks forward to receiving input from these communities with a special interest in input from scientists in LMICs. Some subjects that may be of particular interest include: NIH funding mechanisms and approaches, elements of equitable scientific partnerships, inclusive community research-engagement strategies, practical research capacity building approaches, mutually beneficial data and material sharing approaches, publication access, training and career development, joint leadership strategies, and research priority setting.

For the purposes of this query, global health research collaboration involving scientists and institutions in LMICs are of particular interest. Of note, it is important to recognize that, as a U.S. research funding agency, while NIH welcomes all suggestions, it may be unable to adopt some options identified as potentially beneficial to achieving more equitable global research collaboration. In addition, issues such as equal access to health interventions, the governance of intellectual property sharing, and the equitable distribution of products of research are not within the scope of this RFI.

The NIH seeks comments on any or all of the subjects listed above, and as a starting point poses the following questions:

1. What are the most important elements of equitable global health research?
2. How is equitable global health research conducted? What does this look like in practice?
3. What are the main challenges or barriers to equitable global health research partnerships and the conduct of equitable research?
4. What are the current roles and responsibilities of LMIC researchers and institutions engaged in global health research partnerships? What are the optimal roles and responsibilities of LMIC researchers and institutions engaged in global health research partnerships?

5. Illustrative examples of equitable research partnerships and the way research is conducted between and across the low-, middle-, and high-income countries. What are the characteristics of these partnerships and approaches that make them exemplary?
6. What are key gaps in research capacity that impede equitable global health research?
7. Through the use of peer review, the NIH system is designed to identify and fund highly meritorious applications that address scientific opportunities. In this context, how can a focus on local health priorities and local talent be better integrated to promote global health research equity?
8. What can NIH as a research funder do to promote equitable global health research and research partnerships? Please share any specific suggestions for solutions and strategies.

GCPA & SIDCER Responses

1. What are the most important elements of equitable global health research? Equitable health research, domestically and globally, relies on integrity, ethics, and openness throughout the research process. In order to promote equal and just research practices, the NIH needs to ensure its own research and funding practices are rooted in scientific integrity, transparency toward the public, and openness regarding its funding, data, and publications. It is imperative for equitable global health research that the NIH within its own practices participates in data sharing according to the FAIR principles and data ethics as well as Open Science. The NIH should ensure that its researchers and administrators also provide full transparency regarding their conflicts of interests, including full reporting on their scientific engagements with the public and private sectors (including royalty payments) and with Third Countries. The NIH's role in equitable global health research will be defined by its own openness in science and transparency in its engagements. The NIH should, in addition, ensure that global health research is not defined by partisan politics. As the NIH is a public institution working to support US public health and engaged in global health research, equity – as an investment and an outcome - requires that the funding, the protocols, the data, and the results of all its research belong to the public domain. The aim of equitable global health research is to serve the public good, at home and abroad.
2. How is equitable global health research conducted? What does this look like in practice? Equitable global health research requires that science and medicine globally are treated equally with regard to their evidence base and contributions to public health. Science and medicine should not be judged on the basis of immutable characteristics of persons, including country of origin or country of residence, family history, or sex. Excluding persons and research institutions from participating in research due to current political situations or opinions undermines equity in global health research rendering science and medicine less effective in addressing public health needs, including in crises situations.
3. What are the main challenges or barriers to equitable global health research partnerships and the conduct of equitable research? The main challenges to equitable global health research are
 - a. hegemony in establishing the health research agenda, whether at the global, national, or local level
 - b. the use of political objectives to determine research agenda's
 - c. the failure to promote inclusion due to political and social agenda's
 The major barriers are a. corruption in funding

institutions, recipients of funding, and supporting corrupt political institutions through global health research funding b. the failure to work cooperatively c. a lack of understanding of national and local health research environments outside the United States

4. What are the current roles and responsibilities of LMIC researchers and institutions engaged in global health research partnerships? What are the optimal roles and responsibilities of LMIC researchers and institutions engaged in global health research partnerships? It is unfortunate that the NIH and the RFI COHRED 'Research Fairness Initiative' document (2nd edition, no date) continue to use the pejorative term LMIC for discussing 'equity in global health research'. The quality and value of health research, as well as the expertise and professionalism of researchers, is not defined by the GDP or other economic measures determined by highly powerful international political organizations. When exploring equity in health research, the NIH should begin with, and remain within, evidence-based scientific and medical criteria.
5. Illustrative examples of equitable research partnerships and the way research is conducted between and across the low-, middle-, and high-income countries. What are the characteristics of these partnerships and approaches that make them exemplary? - The Strategic Initiative for Developing Capacity in Ethical Review - PREP - Preparedness Planning for Clinical Research During Public Health Emergencies - Global Forum for Research Ethics and Integrity (GFREI) These partnerships were developed independent of politics (local, national or international), based on openness and integrity in discussion and research, and contributed to data sharing and Open Science.
6. What are key gaps in research capacity that impede equitable global health research? The key gaps that impede equitable global health research arise when there is a failure of funders, researchers, and educators to understand and appreciate the full value and (potential) contribution of persons, institutions, and cultures that are foreign to them.
7. Through the use of peer review, the NIH system is designed to identify and fund highly meritorious applications that address scientific opportunities. In this context, how can a focus on local health priorities and local talent be better integrated to promote global health research equity? Peer review of funding applications within the NIH system, not only is far from sufficient in and of itself to promote local health priorities and local talent, but it is also largely defined by reviewers that are beholden to the NIH in one way or another, whether they are located in the US or elsewhere. The NIH needs to move to a system of independent peer review if it wants to accomplish equitable research at a much broader local levels and promote the development of a wider and more deserving pool of local talent, nationally and internationally.
8. What can NIH as a research funder do to promote equitable global health research and research partnerships? Please share any specific suggestions for solutions and strategies. Partnerships should be supported that are developed on the basis of the expertise appropriate for the scientific and medical needs of the health challenge that is being addressed.